

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**FORMULATION CHARACTERIZATION AND
ANTIBACTERIAL EVALUATION OF HERBAL TOPICAL GEL****K.Tharun kumar*, Dr.T.Mangilal, Nameera Naureen, Asra Jahan, Bysani Jaswanth,
Ayesha Tarannum, Jamgam Sravani**Department of Pharmaceutics, Smt. Sarojini Ramulamma College of Pharmacy, Mahabub
Nagar.-50901, T.G, India.**Abstract:**

*This study aimed to develop and evaluate herbal topical gel formulations with antibacterial properties using ethanolic leaf extracts of *Phyllanthus neruri* and *Heliotropium indicum*. These plants were selected for their established antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial activities. Ethanol was used as the extraction solvent due to its effectiveness in isolating bioactive compounds. Phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of key antibacterial constituents, including flavonoids, phenolics, terpenes, and alkaloids.*

*Four formulations were prepared using 2% carbopol gel base: F1 (control), F2 (*P. neruri* extract), F3 (*H. indicum* extract), and F4 (a 1:1 combination of both). All formulations were evaluated for physical parameters—pH, viscosity, spreadability, and homogeneity—as well as antibacterial efficacy against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* using the agar well diffusion method.*

Among all, F4 exhibited the most significant antibacterial activity, comparable to the standard neomycin sulfate gel, and remained physically and chemically stable under accelerated storage conditions. The findings support the therapeutic potential of these herbal extracts in formulating effective, stable, and natural topical antibacterial gels, offering a promising alternative to synthetic agents with fewer side effects.

Keywords: *Phyllanthus neruri, Heliotropium indicum, Herbal topical gel Antibacterial activity, Ethanolic extract*

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Please cite this article in press **K.Tharun kumar et al., Formulation Characterization And Antibacterial Evaluation Of Herbal Topical Gel., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2025; 12(07).**

INTRODUCTION:

As per WHO medicine is the sum total of the knowledge, skill, and practices based on the theories, beliefs, and experiences indigenous to different cultures, whether explicable or not, used in the maintenance of health as well as in the prevention, diagnosis, improvement or treatment of physical and mental illness.¹ World Health Organization define Traditional herbal medicines as naturally occurring, plant-derived substances with minimal or no industrial processing that have been used to treat illness within local or regional healing practices.² Traditional herbal medicine and their preparations have been widely used for the thousands of years in developing and developed countries owing to its natural origin and lesser side effects.³ These medicines initially took the form of crude drugs such as tinctures, teas, poultices, powders, and other herbal formulations.⁴ The use of plants for healing purposes predates human history and forms the origin of much modern medicine. Clinical, pharmacological, and chemical studies of these traditional medicines, which were derived predominantly from plants, were the basis of most early medicines such as aspirin (willow bark), digitoxin (from foxglove), morphine (from the opium poppy), quinine (from cinchona bark), and pilocarpine (Jaborandi)⁵. Herbal medicine is still the mainstay of about 75 - 80% of the world population, mainly in the developing countries, for primary health care. This is primarily because of the general belief that herbal drugs are without any side effects besides being cheap and locally available. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the use of herbal remedies throughout the world, exceeds that of the conventional drugs by two to three times.⁶

Recently WHO classified herbal medicines into four different classes according to their origin, evolution and forms of current usage.

Indigenous herbal medicines

Herbal medicines in systems

Modified herbal medicines

Imported products with a herbal medicine base

Indigenous herbal medicines are those which historically used in a local community or region and are very well known through long usage by the local population in terms of its composition, treatment and dosage. It can be used freely by the local community or in the local region. However, if the medicines in this category enter the market or go away from the local community or region, they have to meet the requirements of safety and efficacy as per the national regulations for herbal medicines.

Herbal medicines in systems have been used for a long time and are documented with their special theories and concepts, and accepted by the countries. For example, Ayurveda, Unani and Siddha.

Modified herbal medicines have been modified in shape, or form including dose, dosage form, mode of administration, herbal medicinal ingredients, methods of preparation and medical indications. They have to meet the national regulatory requirements of safety and efficacy of herbal medicines.

Imported products with herbal medicine base covers all imported herbal medicines including raw materials and products. Imported herbal medicines must be registered and marketed in the countries of origin. The safety and efficacy data have to be submitted to the national authority of the importing country and need to meet the requirements of safety and efficacy of regulation of herbal medicines in the recipient country.⁷

Ayurveda is Indian system of medicine approximately five thousand year old. The Ayurvedic text is a part of Atharvaveda which belongs to 1500 to 1000 BC. After being transmitted orally for thousands of years, the ancient Ayurvedic texts finally were written and preserved in Sanskrit. Ancient Ayurveda was meant essentially to promote health, however, rather than fight disease. Charak Samhita(1000 BC) and Sushrut Samhita(100 AD) are the main text available. Ayurveda material medica gives detailed descriptions of over 1500 herbs and 10,000 formulations. Madhav Nidan (800 AD) describes diagnostic features and over 5000 signs and symptoms. There are eight branches of study in Ayurveda: Kaya Chikitsa (General Medicine), Kaumara Bhruthya (Paediatrics), Bhutha Vidhya (Psychiatry), Salakya (ENT and Ophthalmology and dentistry), Shalya (Surgery), Agada Tantra (Toxicology), Rasayana (Rejuvenation Therapy) and Vajeekarana (sexual vitality).⁸

Topical Drug Delivery System

The goal of any drug delivery system is to provide a therapeutic amount of drug to the proper site in the body to promptly achieve and then maintain the desired drug concentrations. The route of administration has a significant impact on the therapeutic outcome of a drug. Skin is one of the most readily accessible organs on human body for topical administration and is main route of topical drug delivery system. Topical delivery can be defined as the application of a drug containing formulation to the skin to directly treat cutaneous disorders (e.g. acne) or the cutaneous manifestations of a general disease (e.g. psoriasis) with the intent of containing

the pharmacological or other effect of the drug to the surface of the skin or within the skin. Semi-solid formulation in all their diversity dominates the system for topical delivery, but foams, spray, medicated powders, solutions, as well as medicated adhesive systems are also in use.⁹

Advantages of Topical Drug Delivery System:¹⁰

Avoidance of first pass metabolism

Convenient and easy to apply.

Avoidance of the risks and inconveniences of intravenous therapy and of the varied conditions of absorption, like pH changes, presence of enzymes, Achievement of efficacy with lower total daily dosage of drug by continuous drug input.

Avoids fluctuation in drug levels, inter- and inpatient variations.

Ability to easily terminate the medications, when needed.

A relatively large area of application in comparison

with buccal or nasal cavity

Ability to deliver drug more selectively to a specific site.

Providing utilization of drugs with short biological half-life,

Improving physiological and pharmacological response.

Improve patient compliance.

Provide suitability for self-medication.

Disadvantages of Topical Drug Delivery System

Skin irritation of contact dermatitis may occur due to the drug and/or excipients.

Poor permeability of some drugs through the skin.

Possibility of allergic reactions.

Can be used only for drugs which require very small plasma concentration for action

Enzyme in epidermis may denature the drugs

Drugs of larger particle size not easy to absorb through the skin

Figure 1 Classification of topical preparations

Topical Gels

Topical gels are semi solid homogenous preparation used to cure and treat topical diseases. Gels are more hydrophilic in nature so the rate of released drug or active ingredient was fast. A gel consist of two component, three dimensional cross linked material which contain proportionally large

amount of liquid medium to form adequate rigid network which immobilized the liquid continuous phase.¹⁶ Inorganic particles and organic macromolecules both are used to form a structural network of gel. In chemical gel the particles are associated with permanent covalent bonding while physical topical gels are associated by weaker and reversible secondary intermolecular

forces like hydrogen bonding, electrostatic interactions, hydrophobic interaction and Vander Waals forces.¹¹

Ideal Properties of Topical Gel¹²

The gel should be clear and homogenous.

The gel should be easily broken when shear or force is applied during shaking the container.

The gel should be inert in nature.

The gel should be not sticky.

The gel should be never interacting with other formulation component.

The gel should be stable.

It should not be irate the skin or any part where the gel is applied.

The objective of the current study is

To prepare methanolic extract of the leaves of *Phyllanthus neruri* and *Heliotropium indicum*

To perform preliminary phytochemical analysis of the obtained extracts.

To design and develop single as well as polyherbal gel formulations using the obtained extracts.

To evaluate single as well as polyherbal gel formulations.

To determine *in vitro* anti-microbial effect of the gel formulations.

METHODOLOGY:

Preparation of Extracts

Coarse powdered leaves of *Phyllanthus neruri*¹³ and *Heliotropium indicum*¹⁴ was prepared. 50 g of powder obtained was packed in a muslin cloth and extracted in a Soxhlet extractor with 150ml of methanol for 10 h at 45°C. few pieces of porcelain were added to avoid bumping. The same procedure was followed for both the leaf powders. Both the extracts were collected and then concentrated extract was prepared by heating and removing excess of ethanol. The concentrate thus obtained was further dried by placing in an hot air oven for a period of 1 hour. The individual extracts thus obtained were stored in a tightly closed container.

POWDERED DRIED LEAVES
(*Phyllanthus neruri*)

ETHANOLIC EXTRACTION OF LEAF USING
SOXHLET APPARATUS (*Phyllanthus neruri*)

ETHANOLIC EXTRACTION OF LEAF USING SOXHLET APPARATUS (*Heliotropium indicum*)

POWDERED DRIED LEAVES (*Heliotropium indicum*)

Figure 2 Preparation of ethanolic leaf extracts of the selected plants

CONCENTRATED EXTRACTS

Phytochemical Screening of the Extracts

The extracts obtained by subsequent Soxhlet extraction were subjected to numerous qualitative tests according procedure to work out the presence of various phytoconstituents like alkaloids, glycosides, saponin, flavonoids, carbohydrates, amino acids, sterols, gums and mucilage etc.

Test for carbohydrates Molisch's test

To 2 ml of extract, 2-3 drops of alpha naphthalene solution in alcohol was added and shaken for 2 min. 1 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid was added slowly from the sides of the test tube. A deep violet colour at the junction of two layers indicated the presence of carbohydrates.

Test for saponin Foam test

The extract (50 mg) was diluted with distilled water and made up to 20 ml. The suspension was shaken in a graduated cylinder for 15 min. Appearance of persistent foam indicated the presence of saponins

Test for alkaloids Dragendorff's test

The extract (6 g.) of the plant was dissolved in 10 ml of distilled water then 2 M hydrochloric acid was added until acidify, Dragendorff's reagent (2 ml) was added and an orange red precipitate indicated the presence of alkaloid

Test for glycosides Borntrager's test

For the detection of glycosides, 50 mg of the extract was hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid for 2 h on water bath, filtered and the hydrolysate (4 ml) of filtered hydrolysate was taken in a test tube; 6 ml of chloroform was added and shaken. Chloroform layer was separated and 10% ammonia solution was added to it pink colour indicated the presence of glycosides.

Keller-Killiani Test

This test detects deoxy sugars present in cardiac glycosides.

Extract the plant material with alcohol to it add a few drops of glacial acetic acid containing a trace of ferric chloride. Carefully add concentrated sulfuric acid down the side of the test tube. A brown ring at the interface indicates the presence of deoxy sugars. A violet ring may appear below the brown ring.

Test for terpenes/ sterols

In this test, the extract (20 mg) was taken in chloroform (2 ml) and concentrated sulphuric acid was poured from side of the test tube. The colour of the ring at the junction of the two layers was noted. A violet green colour indicated the presence of cholesterol, sitosterol. A red colour ring showed the

presence of sterol/terpenes.

Test for flavonoids Shimoda test

To dry extract (30 mg), ethanol (2 ml) was added and dropped small piece of Magnesium ribbon. The drop wise addition of conc. HCl leads to the development of colour ranging from orange to red was confirmatory for flavonoids.

Test for phenolics and tannins Ferric chloride test:

The extract (20 mg) was added in 2 ml of 1% ferric chloride solution, a purple or red colour indicated the presence of phenols. One to 2 ml of methanol extract, a few drops of 5% aqueous ferric chloride solution was added. A bluish black colour was produced which disappears on addition of few ml of dilute sulphuric acid followed by the formation of a yellowish-brown precipitate indicated the presence of tannins.

Test for anthraquinone Borntrager test

ml of extract, 3 ml Benzene and 5 ml 10% ammonia solution were added and thereafter shaken properly. Appearance of a pink, red or violet colour in the ammoniacal (lower) phase was taken as the presence of free anthraquinone

Detection of fixed oils and fats**Spot Test**

Press a small quantity of extract separately between two filter papers. Oil stains on the paper indicate the presence of fixed oil.

Saponification Test

Add some drops of 0.5 N alcoholic potassium hydroxide to a little amount of extract beside a drop of phenolphthalein. Heat the mixture on water bath for 1-2 hr. Formation of soap or partial neutralization of alkali indicates the presence of fixed oils and fats.

Preparation of Gel**Preparation of gel base**

The gel base was prepared by dissolving 1g of carbapol in 45ml demineralized water while stirring. care must be taken to prevent the production of agglomerates. Then add the required quantity of triethanolamine to neutralize the pH. Add 5 ml of propylene glycol, stir. To it add the required amount of propyl paraben and 1ml of glycerine was added and stirred for 10 min until a clear and consistent gel base is obtained.

Preparation of herbal gel formulation

Topical gel formulations were prepared using ethanolic leaf extracts of *Phyllanthus neruri* and *Heliotropium indicum*. All the formulations were

prepared by using 2% carbapol gel. Formulation F1 was control formulation where a plain gel without adding the extract was prepared. F2 was prepared by the ethanolic leaf extracts of *Phyllanthus neruri* and F3 by using ethanolic leaf extracts of *Heliotropium*

indicum and F4 was formulated using both ethanolic leaf extracts of *Phyllanthus neruri* and *Heliotropium indicum* taken in the ratio of 1:1 in order to evaluate the synergistic effect of these two extracts.

Table 1 Topical gel formulations:

S.NO	INGREDIENT	F1	F2	F3	F4
		Control			(1:1)
1.	Ethanolic leaf extract of <i>Phyllanthus neruri</i>	-	1g	-	1g
2.	Ethanolic leaf extract of <i>Heliotropium indicum</i>	-	-	1g	1g
3.	Carbapol	1g	1g	1g	1g
4.	Distilled water	Upto 50 ml	Upto 50 ml	Upto 50 ml	Upto 50 ml
5.	Triethanol amine	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s
6.	Glycerine	2ml	2ml	2ml	2ml
7.	Methyl paraben	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
8.	Rose oil	1ml	1ml	1ml	1ml

Figure 3 Preparation of topical herbal gels

Evaluation of Herbal Topical Gel

Various evaluation tests were performed on prepared formulations are as follows:

- Appearance¹⁵
- Determination of Ph¹⁵
- Extrudability¹⁵
- Rheology (Viscosity)¹⁵
- Spread ability¹⁶

Appearance

By visual inspection color, presence of foreign particles and homogeneity of formulations were evaluated.

Determination of pH

The pH of the prepared herbal topical gel was determined by using a digital pH meter. 1 gm of the gel was stirred in distilled water, until a uniform dispersion was formed. It was kept aside for 2 hours. The volume was then made up to 100 ml. Then, the pH was measured. The test was performed in triplicate using a digital pH meter and the mean value \pm SD was calculated.

Extrudability

Extrudability test is based upon the determination of the weight required extruding 0.5 cm ribbon of gel in 10 seconds from lacquered collapsible aluminum tube.

$$\text{Extrudability (\%)} = (X \div Y) \times 100$$

Where; X= Weight of extruded cream from tube; and Y= Weight of cream in tube before extruding.

Rheology (Viscosity)

The viscosity of the formulated batches was determined using a Brookfield Viscometer with spindle 95. The formulation whose viscosity was to be determined was added to the beaker and was allowed to settle down for 30 min at room temperature. Before the measurement was taken, spindle was lowered into the centre of formulation, taking care that spindle does not touch bottom of the beaker and rotated at a speed of 50 rpm. The viscosity reading was noted down and the averages of three readings were taken.

Spreadability

The spreadability of the prepared formulation was determined by parallel plate method. During the measurement using the parallel-plate method, 1 g of the sample prepared in 48 h before the test is placed between two glass plates 20 x 20 cm. A weight (50-500 g) of 125 g is placed on top for 1 minute. Then the diameter of the sample between the plates is measured.

Stability testing based on ICH Q1 Guideline

Accelerated Stability Testing¹⁷

The formulation were packed in the collapsible tube and stored at $40\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}/75\pm 5\%$ R.H. for 4 weeks in stability chamber. Samples were withdrawn at 7 day time interval and evaluated for physical stability.....

Stability of medicinal products may be defined as the capability of a particular formulation in a specific container to remain within its physical, chemical, microbial, therapeutic and toxicological specification, i.e. stability of drug is its ability to resist deterioration. 90% of labeled potency is generally recognized as the minimum acceptable potency level. Deterioration of drug may take several forms arising from changes in physical, chemical and microbiological properties. The changes may affect the therapeutic value of preparation or increase its toxicity.

Antibacterial Studies:

Staphylococcus aureus (Gram +ve) and Escherichia coli (Gram -ve) were used for the determination of the antibacterial activity of various herbal topical gel formulations and standard cup plate methods used for the study. The nutrient agar solution poured into the previously sterilized Petri dishes up to 5 mm thickness. After solidification of the agar microorganisms were added to Petri dishes with a sterilized loop. On each Petri dish, 4 perforations made with a metal tube with a 4 mm diameter to receive test materials, standard and control

respectively. The standard was a commercially available gel and test materials (prepared formulations) added immediately into the wells and kept for incubation at 37°C for 24 h to allow the microorganism to grow and reagents to diffuse through the culture medium. At the end of the incubation, the zone diameter measured with the help of a zone reader¹⁸. Figure 4 *in vitro* antibacterial studies by cup plate method

Organoleptic Characterization

The course powdered leaves of *Phyllanthus neruri* and *Heliotropium indicum* that were collected and the

coarse powder was initially characterized and the observed properties are given in Table

Table 2 Organoleptic characterization of coarse powdered of dried leaves

Character	<i>Phyllanthus neruri</i>	<i>Heliotropium indicum</i>
Colour	Dark green	Dark green
Odour	Characteristic	Characteristic
Taste	Bland	Bitter

The organoleptic properties observed are similar to that of the characters present in the literature, which proves their authenticity.

Phytochemical Screening of the Prepared extracts

The coarse powder obtained were dried, powdered and were extracted with ethanol by continuous hot extraction method using Soxhlet apparatus. The prepared extracts were then screened for the presence of phytochemicals.

Figure 5 Phytochemical Screening of *Phyllanthus neruri* Ethanolic Extract

Figure 6 Phytochemical Screening of *Heliotropium indicum* Ethanolic Extract

Table 3: Phytochemical screening of the extracts

Phytochemical	Phyllanthus neruri	Heliotropium indicum
Carbohydrates	+	+
Saponins	+	+
Alkaloids	+	+
Cardiac glycosides	+	-
Terpenes	+	+
Sterols	+	-
Flavonoids	+	+
Phenolic compounds	+	+
Tannins	+	+
Anthraquinone	+	-
Fixed oils	-	-
Fats	-	-
Reducing sugars	-	+

(+) indicates present, (-) indicates absent

The presence of alkaloid, flavonoids, terpenoids, phenolic compounds and saponins aid in the anti-bacterial property of the extracts.

Alkaloids

These nitrogen-containing compounds can interfere with bacterial DNA and protein synthesis.

Flavonoids

Known for their antioxidant properties, flavonoids can inhibit bacterial growth by damaging bacterial cell walls and membranes.

Terpenoids

These compounds can disrupt bacterial cell membranes, leading to cell lysis.

Phenolic compounds

Including tannins, these compounds can inactivate bacterial enzymes and disrupt microbial cell walls.

Saponins

These have surfactant properties that can

damage bacterial cell membranes.

Evaluation of Herbal Topical Gel

The four herbal topical gels prepared as per the formulae given in Table 3 were further evaluated. Formulation F1 was found to be colourless and the gel formulations F2, F3 and F4 prepared by using the ethanolic extract of the selected plants were in olive green, dark green and army green colours respectively. All the formulations were homogenous and foreign materials were absent. The pH of the formulations were in the range of 7.2 to 7.4. All the formulations had excellent extrudability and the viscosity was in the range 0.3887 to 0.3906 poise. Spreadability determined in terms of spreading area was found to be the best in case of F4 with the highest value of 36.309 cm². The evaluation parameters of the prepared gel formulations (F1 to F4) are given in table.

Table 4: Evaluation of herbal topical gel

Evaluation Parameters	F1	F2	F3	F4
Colour	Translucent	Olive green	Dark green	Army green
Presence of foreign Material	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent
Homogeninty	++	++	++	++
Ph	7.2±0.02	7.4 ± 0.10	7.4 ± 0.01	7.3 ± 0.02
Viscosity (poise)*	0.3887 ± 0.021	0.3891 ± 0.014	0.3906 ± 0.054	0.3872 ± 0.002
Spreadability* (spreading area)	23.75 ± 0.25 cm ²	33.17 ± 0.001 cm ²	28.269 ± 0.014 cm ²	36.309 ± 0.004 cm ²

* Mean ± SD

Anti-bacterial Studies

All the prepared topical gels were further evaluated for anti bacterial effect . Two organism namely Staphylococcus aureus (Gram positive) and Escherichia coli (Gram negative) were used. All the prepared gels were effective against both organisms. Of all 3 formulations , formulation F4 was reported to exhibit highest anti bacterial effect based on

the diameters of zone of inhibitions produced by each. Formulation F4 exhibited almost equal activity as that of standard (neomycin sulphate) in case of *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram positive) where as in case of *Escherichia coli* (Gram negative).

Table 5 Anti-bacterial study of the prepared topical gel

S.NO	FORMULATION	ZONE OF INHIBITION (mm)	
		Staphylococcus Aureus	Escherichia Coli
1	F1	0	0
2	F2	12 ± 0.12	16 ± 0.25
3	F3	14 ± 0.54	19 ± 0.98
4	F4	19 ± 1.25	23 ± 0.54
5	STANDARD	21 ± 0.87	25 ± 1.54

Figure 7 Anti-bacterial activity of prepared topical gel formulation.

Stability Studies

The stability studies of the best herbal gel formulation F4 was performed under accelerated conditions at $40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $75 \pm 5\%$ RH for 4 weeks. There was no marked change in the appearance (colour, foreign material, homogeneity) of the gel. No much variation in the pH of the gel was observed at the end of 4 weeks. Evaluation of the gel for the spreadability also resulted the same values as seen at 0 day. Further, there was no phase separation and microbial contamination in the product for the period under study.

Table 8 Accelerated stability study data of the best herbal topical gel F4

S.NO	PARAMETER	Time interval (in days)				
		0	7	14	21	28
1	Visual Inspection	Complies	Complies	Complies	Complies	Complies
a.	Colour	Army green	Army green	Army green	Army green	Army green
b.	Foreign particles	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent
c.	Homogeneity	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good
2	Ph	7.3	7.3	7.3	7.4	7.4
3	Extrudability	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent
4	Viscosity (poise)*	0.3872 ± 0.002*	0.3752 ± 0.081*	0.3745 ± 0.072*	0.3741 ± 0.002*	0.3741 ± 0.0081*
5	Spreadability*	36.309 ± 0.21	36.214 ± 0.19	36.218 ± 1.19	36.247 ± 0.79	36.287 ± 0.14

* Mean ± SD

CONCLUSION:

The present study successfully demonstrated the formulation and evaluation of herbal topical gels incorporating ethanolic leaf extracts of *Phyllanthus neruri* and *Heliotropium indicum*, both known for their potent pharmacological activities. Phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of bioactive constituents responsible for antibacterial effects, such as flavonoids, terpenes, alkaloids, and phenolic compounds. Among the four formulations developed, the combination formulation (F4) exhibited the most significant antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*, with efficacy comparable to the standard neomycin sulfate gel. F4 also showed favorable physical properties and maintained stability under accelerated storage conditions. These findings highlight the potential of combining plant extracts to develop safe, effective, and stable herbal topical gels as natural alternatives to conventional synthetic antibacterial agents. Further clinical studies are warranted to validate their therapeutic applicability and long-term safety.

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